

“What is the energy that moves the world?”

A Biological Perspective on Emotions, Homeostasis, and Human Energy

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Abstract: This essay explores the complex interaction between the biology of organisms, entropy, and post-agricultural society, with a particular focus on the human organism and mental disorders. From a biological standpoint, the objective and function of the organism are to promote individual and collective homeostasis. Homeostasis refers to the dynamic and constant balance of the organism's internal environment, which is necessary for maintaining health and proper bodily function. This pursuit of homeostasis extends not only to the individual level but also to the collective level, where multicellular organisms work together to maintain overall organismic balance. By exploring human energy in post-agricultural society, it can be observed that this energy, in the form of labor, is the driving force behind all economic activities. However, the introduction of morality into human society may have a significant impact on biological homeostasis, potentially leading to an imbalance that contributes to the development of mental disorders. Understanding these complex interactions between biology, homeostasis, and society may have significant implications for mental health, suggesting that the treatment of mental health conditions may involve the restoration of energy necessary for life and organismic function, both at the individual and collective levels. This understanding can help develop more effective approaches to promoting mental health and well-being in a post-agricultural society.

Keywords: energy, homeostasis, emotions, subjectivity, homeostatic bodily signals, mental disorders, oxygen, ATP, biology, mental health, physiology, morality, post-agricultural society.

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Introduction

This essay aims to explore the relationship between organism biology, homeostasis (individual and collective), and the post-agricultural society, with a special focus on the human organism, its relationship with the environment, and mental disorders. It will discuss how energy and homeostasis are fundamental for the proper functioning of the human organism, both at an individual and collective level. Additionally, it will analyze the impact of the introduction of morality and the mistaken ownership of the human organism on human society and how this can affect homeostasis, both individually and collectively, and contribute to the development of mental disorders. Understanding these complex interactions can provide valuable insights into promoting mental health and well-being in a post-agricultural society.

Life is a complex phenomenon that involves an intricate network of biological processes. In the human organism, survival and reproduction are the main biological objectives, and these functions depend on the organism's ability to maintain homeostasis. Homeostasis is a dynamic process that aims to maintain the internal balance of the organism, ensuring that the conditions essential for its survival are maintained within an appropriate range.

The pursuit of internal balance and the constant regulation of physiological conditions in the organism – homeostasis – are fundamental for maintaining health and proper body functioning. Furthermore, this pursuit of homeostasis also extends to the collective level, where multicellular organisms work together to maintain the organism's overall balance.

Human energy, in the form of work, is the driving force behind all economic activities in the post-agricultural society, powering everything from food production to the creation of advanced technologies. However, this transition to a post-agricultural economy has brought significant changes in the interactions between humans and the environment.

The introduction of morality, social norms, and the issue of mistaken ownership of the human organism has influenced how individuals perceive and respond to stimuli, including emotionally. This influence can trigger imbalances in homeostasis and contribute to the development of mental disorders on a large scale.

It is estimated that currently around 970 million people worldwide live with some form of mental disorder. Therefore, understanding the complex interactions between biology, homeostasis (individual and collective), and society is essential for improving the understanding and treatment of mental health. By recognizing the importance of energy, homeostasis, and the relationship between the human organism and its environment, we can develop more effective approaches to promoting mental health and well-being in a post-agricultural society.

Human Energy in the Post-Agricultural Society: An Underestimated Driving Force

Human energy, in the form of work, is the driving force behind all economic activities, from food production to the creation of advanced technologies. However, in the post-agricultural society, this human energy is no longer directly used to meet basic survival and reproductive needs. Instead, it is traded and bought, used to fuel the economic machine that produces, markets, and consumes goods and services.

Agriculture, which was once humanity's main occupation and an activity closely linked to survival and reproduction, is now only a small part of the global economy. Even this activity is largely mechanized, with human energy being replaced by machines powered by fossil fuels or renewable energy.

However, it is important to remember that it is human energy that allows for the creation and operation of these machines. It is human energy that is used to extract and process the natural resources needed to build and

maintain these machines. And it is human energy that is used to invent and implement the technologies that make these machines possible.

Therefore, although human energy may no longer be directly used for agriculture or other subsistence activities, it is still the driving force behind the entire global economy. And it is this human energy that is traded and bought, enabling the creation, production, trade, and consumption of everything, including agriculture itself.

This situation raises an important question: is it worth it? The transition to a post-agricultural economy has led to an unprecedented increase in wealth and living standards for many people. But it has also led to an imbalance in biological homeostasis, with significant consequences for mental health. The answer to this question, therefore, likely depends on how we value these different outcomes and how we balance human needs and desires with the biological needs of the organism.

Human energy is the fundamental driving force behind all human activities, including agriculture. Even when human energy is seemingly replaced by machines powered by fossil fuels or renewable energy, it is human energy that enables the creation, operation, and maintenance of these machines. Human energy is needed to extract and process natural resources, invent and implement technologies, and operate and maintain the infrastructure that makes these machines possible.

Therefore, although the immediate source of energy for many modern activities may be fossil fuels or renewable energy, the ultimate source of energy is human energy. It is human energy that moves the world.

The Mistaken Ownership of the Human Organism

An important sociocultural change that occurred in the transition to a post-agricultural society is the emergence of the individual as the "owner"

of their own organism, with a distinct subjectivity. This concept can be associated with the development of a more complex individual consciousness and the strengthening of notions of individuality and personal autonomy.

It is impossible for any human-produced product, transportation, trade, and consumption to occur without the free energy of human organisms. The energy generated by human organisms, through the process of respiration and the respiratory chain, is essential to supply the energy demand required for these activities.

Similarly, trade and consumption rely on the energy of human organisms. Energy is necessary to maintain commercial operations, from providing electricity to stores and offices to the work of employees involved in commercial transactions.

From a biological perspective, the concept of being an "owner" of an organism can be considered a deviation, as in reality, we are integrated organisms in larger ecological systems and depend on complex interactions with our environment and other organisms to maintain homeostasis.

This model of self-ownership, along with the emergence of subjectivity, has had profound consequences for homeostasis, both at an individual and collective level. While the strengthening of subjectivity has allowed for greater self-awareness and self-reflection, it has also created a disconnect between the individual and the community, and potentially between the individual and their own body.

Furthermore, this emphasis on individualism and autonomy can make it difficult to maintain collective homeostasis. In a social group, homeostasis is maintained through cooperation and mutual support. If individuals prioritize self-protection over cooperation, this destabilizes the balance of the group.

Before the advent of agriculture, humans lived in a more integrated manner with the natural environment and consequently had a stronger collective approach to maintaining homeostasis. The survival of the group depended on cooperation among members and maintaining a balance with the surrounding ecosystem. Therefore, we can say that there was a higher level of collective homeostasis.

In hunter-gatherer societies, people lived in small, mobile groups that relied on immediate natural resources for their survival. This group life necessitated cooperation, where each individual contributed to the homeostasis of the group.

Objective and Function of the Human Organism

Survival is one of the main biological objectives of any organism. In the case of humans, this involves ensuring that basic needs are met, such as food, water, shelter, and protection against external dangers. To fulfill this objective, the human organism has systems and mechanisms that allow for the search and attainment of these essential resources.

Another fundamental biological objective is reproduction. Humans are sexual beings, meaning that reproduction occurs through the union of male and female sex cells, namely sperm and egg cells. The reproductive function aims to ensure the perpetuation of the species, allowing genes to be passed on to the next generation. In the post-agricultural era, these objectives have been altered and used for other purposes.

Additionally, the human organism also seeks to maintain homeostasis, which is a state of internal balance necessary for proper body functioning. Homeostasis involves the regulation of different physiological variables, such as body temperature, glucose levels, blood pH, ion concentration, among others. This regulation is carried out through control systems, such as the nervous system and endocrine system, which constantly monitor and adjust the organism's internal conditions to keep it within an appropriate range.

In addition to these fundamental objectives, the human organism also performs various specific functions that are essential for life, such as respiration, digestion, blood circulation, the immune system, the nervous system, the musculoskeletal system, among others. Each of these functions contributes to the proper functioning of the organism as a whole and the maintenance of life.

Individual and Collective Homeostasis: The Human Organism's Continuous Pursuit of Balance and Harmony

From a biological standpoint, the objective and function of the human organism are to promote individual and collective homeostasis. Homeostasis refers to the dynamic and constant balance of the organism's internal environment, which is necessary for maintaining health and proper bodily function.

To achieve homeostasis, the human organism possesses self-regulatory mechanisms that monitor and adjust various physiological parameters, such as body temperature, acid-base balance, blood glucose concentration, blood pressure, water balance, and many others. These mechanisms are crucial in ensuring that the organism's internal conditions are maintained within an optimal range, even in the face of external fluctuations.

Homeostasis is not limited to the individual level but also extends to the collective level. In multicellular organisms, individual cells work together to maintain the homeostasis of the organism as a whole. Each cell has specialized functions that contribute to the harmonious functioning of the system.

Additionally, the human organism also has social regulation systems that promote cohesion and cooperation among individuals. These social systems help ensure the survival and prosperity of the group as a whole, favoring the maintenance of collective homeostasis.

The pursuit of individual and collective homeostasis is essential for the survival and adaptation of the human organism. When there is an imbalance or dysfunction in these regulatory mechanisms, health problems and disruptions in individual and collective well-being can arise.

Thus, the biological function of the human organism is to promote individual and collective homeostasis, ensuring a balanced internal environment and harmonious functioning of the organism as a whole. This pursuit of homeostasis is a fundamental principle of biology and human physiology.

Emotions as Homeostatic Bodily Signals

Emotions are often considered subjective experiences, but in this essay, we argue that they are best understood as 'homeostatic bodily signals.' These signals are physiological responses to stimuli that aim to maintain the body's homeostasis. Homeostasis is the body's ability to maintain a stable internal state despite changes in the external environment. Emotions, therefore, play a crucial role in maintaining this internal stability (Orquiza, J. C. (2023)[1].

For example, when we face a threat, we experience homeostatic bodily signals of fear. This emotion triggers a series of physiological responses, such as increased heart rate and the release of stress hormones, that prepare the body to respond to the threat. This is an example of how an emotion serves as a homeostatic bodily signal, helping the body maintain homeostasis in the face of external challenges (Orquiza, J. C. (2023)[1].

Similarly, the emotion of happiness can be seen as a signal that the body is in a state of balance or homeostasis. When we are happy, our body is generally in a state of relaxation and contentment, indicating that our basic needs are being met and that there are no immediate threats to our survival (Orquiza, J. C. (2023)[1].

This perspective on emotions as homeostatic bodily signals has significant implications for our understanding of mental health. If emotions are signals that help the body maintain homeostasis, then mental health conditions can be seen as imbalances in the body's homeostasis. For example, chronic anxiety can be seen as a signal that the body is constantly in a 'fight or flight' state, even in the absence of real threats. Similarly, depression can be seen as a signal that the body is in a state of discouragement or hopelessness, which may be a response to a perceived threatening or resource-deprived environment (Orquiza, J. C. (2023)[1].

This perspective suggests that the treatment of mental health conditions may involve restoring the energy necessary for life and the functioning of the organism, at both the individual and collective levels (Orquiza, J. C. (2023)[1].

The Illusion of Subjectivity

Subjectivity is a deeply personal and individual experience that appears to be the product of the complex interaction of biological processes. However, from a biological perspective, subjectivity can be seen as a kind of 'illusion' created by the intricate interplay of these biological processes.

Each cell in our body contributes to the experience of being a 'self.' Subjectivity is therefore the result of the interaction of nearly 30 trillion cells, each contributing its small part to the experience of being a 'self.' This perspective may sound strange but is supported by an increasing understanding of biology and neuroscience.

Subjectivity, then, is not something that exists independently of the body but is deeply rooted and intertwined with it. The experience of being a 'self' is therefore a bodily experience, an experience that is profoundly influenced and mediated by cellular and physiological processes. The importance of oxygen in maintaining homeostasis and the lived experience

of homeostasis are discussed to illustrate the importance of homeostasis for subjective experience and emotions (Bouayed et al., 2009)[2].

This perspective has significant implications for our understanding of mental health. If subjectivity is so deeply rooted in the body, then mental health conditions can be seen as imbalances in the body's homeostasis. Treating these conditions may involve restoring the energy necessary for life, for the functioning of the organism, that is, nearly 30 trillion interconnected cells that allow the existence of the human organism, moment to moment.

Subjectivity and Emotions as Products of Cellular Homeostasis

Subjectivity and human emotions are intrinsically linked to cellular homeostasis, a dynamic balance that our body seeks to maintain to ensure proper functioning. Cellular homeostasis is influenced by a variety of factors, including oxidative stress, which has been associated with a range of mental health conditions, including anxiety and depression.

Oxidative stress occurs when there is an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the body's ability to counteract their harmful effects. This can lead to cellular damage and has been implicated in a variety of diseases, including neurodegenerative disorders and psychiatric disorders.

Anxiety, for example, is an emotional response to a perceived threat and is accompanied by emotional stress, which involves behavioral, expressive, and physiological characteristics. When this emotion is inappropriate, extreme, and persistent, it is classified as pathological. Anxiety is implicated in a range of psychiatric disorders, such as depression, panic attacks, phobias, generalized anxiety disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and post-traumatic stress disorder.

Recent studies have established a connection between oxidative stress and certain anxiety disorders, showing that other systems, such as oxidative metabolism, may affect anxiety regulation. These findings, which establish a link between oxidative stress and pathological anxiety, have inspired a series of other recent studies focused on the link between oxidative status and normal anxiety and on a possible causal relationship between cellular oxidative stress and emotional stress.

In summary, subjectivity and human emotions are not just products of our thoughts and experiences but are also deeply influenced by cellular homeostasis and the biochemical balance in our bodies. Understanding these connections can open new pathways for the treatment of a variety of mental health conditions.

Prenatal Human Development and Cell Quantity

Prenatal human development is a complex process involving the formation of millions to billions of cells. Starting with a single cell, the zygote, the human embryo develops through a series of stages, each involving a dramatic increase in cell number (Moore & Persaud, 2008; Gilbert, 2014)[4].

During the zygote stage, which lasts from zero to three days, there are only one or two cells. In the morula stage, which occurs from four to five days, the number of cells increases to 16 to 32. In the blastocyst stage, which occurs from six to seven days, the number of cells increases to 100 to 200. During implantation and gastrulation, which occur from seven to 14 days, the number of cells increases to hundreds. During the embryonic period, which occurs from two to eight weeks, the number of cells increases to millions to billions. Finally, during the fetal period, which occurs from eight weeks until birth, the number of cells increases to millions to 100 billion (Moore & Persaud, 2008; Gilbert, 2014)[4].

This rapid increase in cell number during prenatal development is an impressive example of the human body's ability to maintain homeostasis

even in the face of dramatic changes. Each of these cells contributes to the experience of being a 'self,' and subjectivity is therefore the result of the interaction of nearly 30 trillion cells, each contributing its small part to the experience of being a 'self.'

Distribution of Cells in the Human Body

The human body is composed of trillions of cells, each playing a specific role in maintaining homeostasis. The distribution of these cells varies widely, with the majority of cells being erythrocytes, or red blood cells, representing 83.9% of the total cells (Bianconi et al., 2013)[3].

Other cells, such as platelets, which represent 4.9% of the total cells, bone marrow cells, which represent 2.5% of the total cells, surface endothelial cells, which represent 2.1% of the total cells, lymphocytes, which represent 1.6% of the total cells, hepatocytes, which represent 0.8% of the total cells, dermal fibroblasts, which represent 0.1% of the total cells, bronchial endothelial cells, epithelial cells, interstitial respiratory cells, each representing 0.5% of the total cells, glial cells, which represent 0.3% of the total cells, neurons, which represent 0.3% of the total cells, adipocytes, which represent 0.2% of the total cells, muscle cells, which represent 0.001% of the total cells, and other cells, which represent 2.0% of the total cells, make up the remaining cell distribution (Bianconi et al., 2013)[3].

The total number of cells is estimated at 29.7 trillion. These numbers are estimations and can vary depending on various factors, including the size and age of the individual (Bianconi et al., 2013)[3].

Implications for Mental Health

Understanding emotions as 'homeostatic bodily signals' and subjectivity as a product of the interaction of nearly 30 trillion cells has

significant implications for mental health. If emotions are 'homeostatic bodily signals,' then mental health conditions can be seen as imbalances in the body's homeostasis (Orquiza, J. C. (2023)[1].

For example, anxiety can be seen as a response to a perceived threat to the body's homeostasis, whether that threat is real or imagined. Similarly, depression can be seen as a response to a perceived loss of homeostasis, whether that loss is real or imagined.

This suggests that the treatment of mental health conditions may involve restoring the organism's homeostasis.

The Lived Experience of Homeostasis: The Role of Oxygen

To understand the importance of homeostasis and the complex interaction of biological processes that sustain it, we can consider the role of oxygen in our body. As mentioned earlier, the majority of cells in the human body are erythrocytes, or red blood cells, representing 83.9% of the total cells. One of the main functions of erythrocytes is to transport oxygen from the lungs to the rest of the body.

Oxygen is crucial for the production of ATP, the primary source of energy for cells. Without oxygen, ATP production ceases, leading to a disruption of homeostasis and eventually the death of the organism.

To experience the importance of oxygen and the need for homeostasis, I invite you to do a simple experiment. Try holding your breath and see how long you can go without breathing. You will notice that after a short period, you will start to feel discomfort and distress. This is because as the oxygen level in your blood decreases, the body initiates a series of physiological responses to restore the energy necessary for life. These responses include an increased heart rate and the sensation of shortness of breath, which serves as a signal for you to start breathing again.

This simple experiment illustrates the importance of homeostasis and the role that 'emotions' or 'homeostatic bodily signals' play in maintaining life. The discomfort and distress you feel when holding your breath is an example of how the body uses these signals to protect itself and maintain the energy necessary for life.

Energy Required for the Maintenance of Human Subjectivity

The maintenance of human subjectivity, or the experience of being a 'self,' requires a significant amount of energy. This energy is necessary to maintain the body's homeostasis, allowing cells to function efficiently and biological processes to occur in an orderly manner. Oxygen plays a crucial role in energy production through the process of cellular respiration, where it is used to produce ATP, the primary source of energy for cells (Alberts et al., 2002).

The lack of oxygen, or hypoxia, can lead to a decrease in ATP production, resulting in a decrease in cellular efficiency and potentially cellular damage that can lead to the death of the organism.

Furthermore, the amount of energy required to maintain human subjectivity is substantial. It is estimated that the human brain, which is responsible for many aspects of subjectivity, uses about 20% of the body's total energy despite representing only 2% of the total body mass (Mink et al., 1981). This energy is used to maintain neural activity, including signal transmission between neurons, maintenance of cell membrane polarization, and neurotransmitter synthesis.

In summary, the maintenance of human subjectivity is a process that requires a significant amount of energy. This energy is necessary to maintain the homeostasis of the body and to enable biological processes to occur efficiently. The lack of energy can lead to a decrease in cellular

efficiency and a range of health problems, including mental health conditions.

Morality, Homeostasis, and Post-Agricultural Society

The introduction of morality into human society is a complex phenomenon with profound implications for biological homeostasis. Morality, with its rules and norms, imposes a structure of behavior that may not align with the biological needs of the human organism. This can lead to an imbalance in homeostasis, the body's ability to maintain a stable internal state.

Moreover, morality can influence self-perception and perception of others. Emotions are seen as 'homeostatic bodily signals,' physiological responses to stimuli that aim to maintain the body's homeostasis. If morality leads to chronic negative 'homeostatic bodily signals,' such as guilt or shame, this can disrupt homeostasis and contribute to the development of mental disorders (Orquiza, J. C. (2023)[1].

The HPA system, which regulates energy and therefore the homeostasis of nearly 30 trillion cells in the human organism, is often activated beyond what is 'allowed' in the new post-agricultural social scheme due to the intervention of moral rules and norms. This can cause an imbalance far beyond what was programmed in the design of the human organism, resulting in mental disorders.

In summary, the introduction of morality into human society can have a significant impact on biological homeostasis, potentially leading to an imbalance that may contribute to the development of mental disorders. A deeper understanding of these biological and moral processes can have significant implications for mental health, suggesting that the treatment of mental health conditions may involve restoring the energy necessary for life and the functioning of the organism as a whole.

Discussion

In this essay, we have explored the complex interaction between organism biology, individual and collective homeostasis, and post-agricultural society. We have focused on the human organism and discussed the importance of human energy for maintaining homeostasis and proper body functioning. We have also considered the relationship between homeostasis, emotions, and subjectivity, and how these processes are interconnected.

An important question that arises from our argument is the relationship between individual and collective homeostasis. Each cell in the human organism contributes to individual homeostasis, meaning the balance and regulation of internal body conditions. However, it is also through cooperation and interaction between cells that collective homeostasis is maintained. Understanding this interconnection between individual and collective homeostasis is crucial for establishing a holistic approach to health and well-being.

In a post-agricultural society, the introduction of morality and social norms, along with the misguided notion of human ownership, can affect biological homeostasis. The rules and norms of society may impose behavior that is not aligned with the biological needs of the human organism, leading to an imbalance in homeostasis. This can contribute to the emergence of mental disorders, such as anxiety and depression.

However, by understanding the crucial role of human energy in maintaining life and organism functioning, we can develop more effective approaches to promoting mental health and well-being in a post-agricultural society. This may involve

restoring the energy required for life and organism functioning in all its nearly thirty trillion cells. Understanding the complex interaction between individual and collective biology and society is crucial for developing strategies that promote both individual and collective mental health.

In conclusion, the interaction between organism biology, individual and collective homeostasis, and post-agricultural society is a complex and multifaceted topic. By recognizing the importance of human energy in maintaining homeostasis and organism functioning, and understanding the implications of morality for biological homeostasis, we can develop a deeper understanding of mental disorders and seek more effective approaches to mental health and human well-being. In this context, it is essential to recognize the importance of homeostasis in the development and promotion of mental health, both at an individual and collective level.

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